

Polarographic Study of the Composition and Stability Constants of Formate Complexes of Lead

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Reduction of lead in formate solution is a reversible and diffusion-controlled process. The half-wave potential shifts towards more negative value with the increase of formate concentration, indicating the complex formation. The composition and stability constants have been calculated by DeFord and Hume's method. Presence of three complex species: $\text{Pb}(\text{HCOO})^+$, $\text{Pb}(\text{HCOO})_2$, and $\text{Pb}(\text{HCOO})_3^-$ has been indicated. The overall formation constants at 30° have been found to be 7.0, 9.5, and 14.0 respectively ($\mu=1.0$). The percentage distribution of lead in various forms as a function of formate concentration has been presented.

The polarography of lead in complexing and noncomplexing supporting electrolytes was studied by a number of workers¹⁻¹⁰ and lead was found to form many complexes in solution with various complexing agents. During polarographic reduction of lead in various complexing agents, lead was found to reduce reversibly in formate solution, the reduction having been noticed to be a diffusion-controlled process. The present communication deals with the determination of the composition and stability constants of formate complexes of lead.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade purity. The solution of lead was prepared by dissolving a weighed amount of lead nitrate in conductivity water and standardised as usual. Potassium nitrate was used to keep a constant ionic strength since with sodium perchlorate precipitation occurred. Potassium formate was used as a complexing agent.

The L. P. 55 polarograph (Heyrovsky system) was used manually for obtaining current-voltage curves. The capillary had the following characteristics: $m=1.746$ mg./sec. and $t=4.2$ sec. (at -1.0 V vs. S. C.E. in $0.1 M$ potassium nitrate solution). All the measurements were done at $30^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$, which was kept constant by means of Haake type ultra thermostat. A H-type cell, saturated with potassium chloride-agar agar bridge, was used during all the measurements. All the half-wave potentials refer to the saturated calomel electrode.

*Presented at 3rd. Annual Convention of the Indian Chemical Society, held at Aligarh in December, 1965.

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Solutions containing 1 mM Pb²⁺ and 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.9, and 1.0 M potassium formate were prepared. Ionic strength was kept constant ($\mu=1.0$) by adding the requisite amount of potassium nitrate. Triton X₁₀₀ (0.001% in final solution) was added as maximum suppressor. Purified nitrogen was passed through each solution for removal of dissolved oxygen.

TABLE I
Analysis of F_1 ($[X]$) functions.

C_x .	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs. S.C.E.)	i_d (divisions)	Slope. (mv)	$F_0([X])$.	$F_1([X])$.	$F_2([X])$.	$F_n([X])$.
0.0M	0.4008	73.5	33.0	..	..	..	..
0.1	0.4082	73.5	32.0	1.762	7.62	..	..
0.2	0.4152	74.0	34.0	2.990	9.95	12.2	13.5
0.3	0.4192	73.0	34.0	4.090	10.30	9.1	..
0.4	0.4264	72.0	33.5	7.053	13.10	14.0	13.5
0.5	0.4287	73.0	33.0	8.478	15.00	15.0	11.0
0.6	0.4338	73.5	32.0	12.530	12.58	18.3	14.5
0.8	0.4405	73.0	32.0	20.040	24.90	21.7	15.0
1.0	0.4460	73.0	33.0	31.920	30.00	23.4	14.0

DISCUSSION

In each case, a single well-defined reduction wave appeared. The plots of i_d vs. $\sqrt{h}$ (height of the mercury column after applying the back-pressure correction) and i_d vs. concentration of lead were found to be linear and pass through the origin. The above results indicate that the reduction is diffusion-controlled. The plots of $\log i/(i_d-i)$ vs. $E_{d.}$ were found to be linear with a slope of the order of 31 ± 2 mv, showing the reversibility of the reduction. The value of 'n' was found to be 2. The diffusion current was not found to change appreciably with increasing concentration of the formate ion, indicating that the diffusion coefficients of aqueo-lead ion and lead formate complexes did not differ very much in size. The half-wave potential was found to shift towards more negative values with increasing formate concentration, showing the formation of the complexes between lead and formate ion.

A plot of half-wave potential vs. $-\log C_x$ (C_x =formate concentration in M) is found to be a smooth curve, instead of a straight line (Fig. 1), which shows the presence of two or more complexes. The classical method due to Lingane¹¹ could not be applied for the calculation of the composition and stability constants of the complexes. For this purpose DeFord and Hume's method¹² has been used.

It was shown by DeFord and Hume¹² that the shift in half-wave potential due to complex formation can be expressed as

$$\Delta E_{1/2} = (E_{1/2})_0 - (E_{1/2})_a = \frac{2.303RT}{nF} \log_{10} Y_M \frac{I_0}{I_a} \sum_0^N \frac{\beta_j \{X\}^j}{Y_{MX_j}} \quad \dots (1)$$

11. *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, 29, 1.

12. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 73, 5321, 5323.

where $(E_1)_0$ and $(E_1)_s$ are the half-wave potentials of the complex and simple metal ions, respectively; R , T and F have their usual significance; n denotes the number of electrons; I_s and I_0 are the experimental diffusion currents for simple and all complex, ions respectively; β_j is the overall formation constant of the j th complex; $\{X\}$ is the activity of the complexing ligand and Y_M and Y_{MX_j} denote the activity coefficients at the electrode surface of the metal and complex species, respectively. Equation (1) can be rearranged to define a function $F_0(\{X\})$ such that

$$F_0(\{X\}) = \text{antilog}_{10} \left[\frac{0.4343nF}{RT} \Delta E_1 + \log \frac{I_s}{I_0} \right] = Y_M \sum_0^N \frac{\beta_j [X]^j}{Y_{MX_j}}$$

$$= 1 + \beta_1 [X] \frac{Y_M Y_X}{Y_{MX_1}} + \beta_2 [X]^2 \frac{Y_M (Y_X)^2}{Y_{MX_2}} + \dots \quad (2)$$

$$F_1(\{X\}) = \{F_0(\{X\}) - 1\} / [X] = \beta_1 + \beta_2 [X] + \beta_3 [X]^2 + \dots \quad (3)$$

$$F_2(\{X\}) = \{F_1(\{X\}) - \beta_1\} / [X] = \beta_2 + \beta_3 [X] + \dots \quad (4)$$

$$F_3(\{X\}) = \{F_2(\{X\}) - \beta_2\} / [X] = \beta_3 + \beta_4 [X] + \dots \quad (5)$$

where $[X]$ denotes the concentration of the complexing ligand and Y 's are the corresponding activity coefficients. β_0 , β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 are the overall formation constants of the zero complex and the complex containing one, two, and three ligands, respectively.

FIG. 1. Plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs. $-\log C_x$ for lead-formate system.

FIG. 2. $F_j(\{X\})$ plots for lead-formate system. $[O] F_0(\{X\})$; $[\Delta] F_1(\{X\})$; $[\square] F_2(\{X\})$; $[X] F_3(\{X\})$

The experimentally determined values of half-wave potentials together with $F_j(\{X\})$ values calculated from equations (1) to (5) are recorded in Table I, assuming that the ionic atmosphere and, therefore the several activity coefficients, probably change very little since the ionic strength is constant. The overall formation constants were obtained by a graphical extrapolation of the $F_j(\{X\})$ functions to the zero ligand concentration

(Fig. 2). The overall formation constants of the three complexes formed: $\text{Pb}(\text{HCOO})^+$, $\text{Pb}(\text{HCOO})_2$, and $\text{Pb}(\text{HCOO})_3^-$ at 30° come to be 7.0, 9.5, and 14.0 respectively ($\mu=1.0$).

The percentage distribution of lead present in various forms as a function of logarithm of formate-ion concentration has been calculated by equations (6) and (7):

$$\frac{[M]}{C_M} = \frac{1}{F_o([X])} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\frac{[\text{MX}_j]}{C_M} = \frac{\beta_j [X]^j}{F_o([X])} \quad \dots (7)$$

(where $[M]$ denotes the concentration of uncomplexed metal ions; $[\text{MX}_j]$, the concentration of the complex species and the C_M , the total metal ion added to the system). The results have been presented in Fig. 3. The percentage variation is about ± 5.0 .

FIG. 3. Percentage distribution of various species present in lead-formate system.
 $(O) M_0^{2+}$; MX_{1+} ; $(\square) MX_2$; $(X) MX_{3-}$.

It is clear that the complex species are very weak, establishing the validity of the above method for determination of the composition and the stability constants of very weak complexes. The reduction of lead in formate solution is diffusion-controlled; thus lead can be estimated polarographically in formate media.

The authors wish to express their thanks to the U. G. C., New Delhi, for sanctioning a fellowship to one of them (D.S.J.) and to Prof. R.C. Mehrotra, Head of the Chemistry Department, for providing facilities.